

iMagine

First Communication, Dissemination and Engagement plan

iMagine deliverable 2.1

31/01/2023

Abstract

This deliverable provides an overview on how project results, developments and branding will be communicated. Moreover, a plan for the engagement with the targeted audiences, a dissemination strategy, the description of promotion, outreach, training and co-design activities are presented in the document along with a dissemination plan.

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Introduction

iImagine aims to deploy, operate, validate, and promote a dedicated iImagine AI framework and platform. The platform connected to the EOSC and AI4EU provides researchers in aquatic sciences with open access to a diverse portfolio of AI-based image analysis services and image repositories from multiple RIs. These services and repositories are relevant to the overarching theme of 'Healthy oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters'.

The project concept revolves around three main working blocks:

- A common **iImagine AI framework and computing platform** facilitating researchers in developing, testing, training, hosting, and operating AI-based image analysis services, following FAIR practices.
- **Five operational and three prototype AI-based image analysis services** with image repositories will be deployed at the iImagine AI platform to provide open access and exploitation by researchers. They will also be instrumental in demonstrating value and fostering further uptake by a large community of target users and beneficiaries.
- **Best Practices** – consisting of documentation and training materials; they give practical guidance and examples to end-users on exploiting image datasets and analysis applications offered by the iImagine portfolio and serve as an example to whoever wishes to develop and deliver similar AI-based image analysis services and image repositories.

The activities related to dissemination, communication and events in iImagine will be planned and undertaken as part of WP2 – Exploitation and Innovation Management, fall under task 2.2, and with the objectives:

- to coordinate communication activities within the project,
- to analyse the target communities benefiting from project outputs,
- to develop strategies for communicating the benefits in a way that is relevant to them (in collaboration with T2.1);
- to monitor the scientific landscape in marine and aquatic research, and coordinates project outreach and service promotion activities towards relevant audiences;
- to organise webinars, annual workshops, online and face-to-face events targeting the main audience groups and arrange contributions from WP3-4-5 to relevant external events, in the form of presentation, posters, demos, workshops; and
- to deliver FitSM training and consultancy for service providers within the consortium to help them increase their TRL by adopting mature service management approaches.

This deliverable provides an overview of how the project will communicate its results, developments, and branding. Moreover, it includes a plan to engage with the targeted audiences, a dissemination strategy, the description of promotion, outreach, training and co-design activities.

Purpose of the document

In this first deliverable, D2.1, the overall plan for these activities is laid out, mapped to target audiences, set against a timeline, and matched with a suitable set of indicators for success. It includes a plan to engage with the targeted audiences, a dissemination strategy, and a description of promotion, outreach, training and co-design activities. This initial plan is based on the project proposal and improved with findings and results (including M2.1: organisation of the Kick-off event and M2.2: communication package and launch website) from the first five months of the project. This plan will be updated in M20 (D2.4) and concluded with a final report by M36 (D2.8).

Structure of the document

The document follows this structure:

- An overview of the target groups identified to be relevant for the project engagement and communication
- An overview of the project Key Exploitable Results, and how they relate to the target groups and the project identified outcomes and impact
- A list of the communications channels and available assets
- An overview of the ways to measure progress and impact

Target groups

The identified stakeholders with whom iMagine will engage with and interact belong to seven major target groups:

- Users (researchers, research organisations, research infrastructures)
- Service and content providers
- Infrastructure providers
- Similar AI initiatives and the EOSC
- Private sector
- Policy and decision makers
- Organisations/agencies from different disciplines
- General public

The table below describes the target groups and the identified ways for iMagine to engage with them. In the following iteration of this document, the ways of engagement could be further refined and expanded based on the experience gained in the first period of the project activity.

Tier 1: Interact directly with iMagine services and outcomes

Tier 2: Benefit from iMagine services and can influence them, but rarely interact directly with iMagine services

Tier 3: Either affect or are affected by the iMagine services and outcomes, but don't interact or directly use iMagine services

Figure 1. Target User Segmentation

Target group	Examples of Entities covered under this stakeholder group	Description
Users (tier 1)	Research Infrastructures Data Scientists and Modelers Marine Researchers Environmental Managers International Projects SMEs and Large Companies Public and Private Research Organisations	<p>The target group of the users consists of any audience that will make use of the iImagine AI services and data repositories as soon as they become available through the dedicated AI platform. Research infrastructures, research organisations and researchers from both public and private organisations belong to this group.</p> <p>The users are key in understanding the outcomes of the project and their impact, and will be able to use the services and the AI platform to enhance their research. Moreover, through their networks, they will be a valid aid to iImagine in helping further dissemination of the useful assets available to the end users (here meant as anyone that could make use of the results and insights generated by researchers through the iImagine platform and services. These end users can be both from the public and private sector).</p>
Service and content providers (tier 1)	Software Developers	This group is composed of those providers

Target group	Examples of Entities covered under this stakeholder group	Description
	Computer Scientists	that will be integrated in the iMagine AI framework with their AI services and aquatic science-related content. Those assets will be highlighted in the iMagine portfolio and be accessible using the Virtual Access.
Infrastructure providers (tier 1)	HTC/Cloud providers Storage providers E-infrastructure & Commercial Cloud providers	This group is made of any provider of infrastructure services that could be used by the Use Cases (UC) to run their research, or by the iMagine AI platform to run its services.
Similar AI initiatives (tier 2)	EOSC AI4EU	The stakeholders in this group belong to similar AI initiatives to iMagine funded under Horizon Europe, such as the AI4EU project. Those initiatives could benefit from the project results by being aware of the project's outputs that support the same cause. This should lead to coordinated dissemination activities.
Private sector (tier 2)	Suppliers SMEs and Large Organisations	This group targets private organisations, such as engineering units and consultancies, that are involved in environmental monitoring and managing

Target group	Examples of Entities covered under this stakeholder group	Description
		activities. They could use the outcomes of iImagine (guidelines, best practices, AI platform, AI services, and documentation in general) to learn more about ways to enhance their work and overall benefit from the outcomes of the use cases.
Organisations/agencies from different disciplines (tier 3)	NGOs Interpol International Maritime Organisation United Nations Trade Associations	The target group gathers organisations such as NGOs and specialised training centres in aquatic science that will benefit from the project results. This type of audience would be able to use the services and other outcomes of the project and the resulting impact for lobby, training material/content and awareness-raising purposes of the specific disciplines.
Policy makers (tier 3)	EU and National Governments Environmental Ministry Mission Ocean HE Funding Agencies	Policy makers could leverage on the project results to reinforce existing policies and directives about environment and marine science, more specifically.
Decision makers (tier 3)	National Authorities Local Authorities	Decision makers and local authorities will be demonstrated the environmental and

Target group	Examples of Entities covered under this stakeholder group	Description
	Funding Agencies	societal impact the project outcomes contribute to; as a result, they could be convinced to change national policies accordingly.
General public (tier 3)	Citizens	Anyone interested in the outcomes of the project to learn about the status of marine science research.

Table 1. Target groups and description

Use cases and their connection with stakeholders

iMagine supports eight use cases to develop and deploy specific AI supported image analytical services, thereby refining and making the AI platform more robust while also contributing to the development of marine science image repositories. The table below presents the use cases, both the mature and the prototype ones, the topic addressed (that will serve as a category to present them in the dissemination) and the stakeholders each of them identified as already existing target audiences or future ones - in the case of the prototype use cases. The use cases are also connected to the most relevant Research Infrastructures in the marine science domain.

Use case	Topic(s)	Target groups addressed or potentially addressed
UC1: Aquatic Litter Drones: Aquatic Litter monitoring system using drones	Pollution (Aquatic Litter), Creating awareness and engaging citizens	NGO's, Monitoring agencies, Researchers, Environmental managers, MSFD and WFD communities.
UC2: Zooscan – EcoTaxa pipeline: Taxonomic identification of zooplankton using Zooscan	Biodiversity, Climate Change	Researchers, Environmental managers
UC3: Ecosystem monitoring at EMSO sites by video imagery	Biodiversity, Creating awareness and engaging citizens.	Researchers, EMSO Data managers, Environmental managers, Citizens
UC4: Oil Spill Detection: Oil spill detection from satellite images	Pollution (Oil spills)	Researchers, Monitoring agencies, Environmental managers, EMSA
UC5: Flowcam phytoplankton identification: Taxonomic identification of phytoplankton using Flowcam images	Biodiversity, Climate Change	Researchers, Environmental managers
UC6-P: Underwater Noise Identification: Underwater noise identification from	Pollution (Underwater Noise)	Researchers, Environmental Agencies

Use case	Topic(s)	Target groups addressed or potentially addressed
acoustic recordings using spectrograms		
UC7-P: Beach Monitoring: Posidonia oceanica berms and rip-currents detection from video monitoring systems	Ecosystem health – Coastal developments – Climate Change	Researchers, Environmental Agencies, Beach Safety Authorities, Lifeguards, Government Institutions
UC8-P: Freshwater diatoms identification: Identification of freshwater diatoms using microscopic images	Biodiversity, Climate Change, Pollution (Freshwaters)	Researchers, Environmental managers (water agencies, private consultancies), Teachers (biodiversity, biomonitoring)

Table 2. Use cases in iMagine, covered topics and addressed stakeholders

Figure 2. Relations between use cases and relevant Research Infrastructures in the field

iMagine overarching outputs and impact

During the project duration, iMagine will significantly contribute to aquatic environmental research and aquatic management, governance, and socio-economic activities, with a resulting impact on the broader European research landscape.

The expected outcomes of the projects are grouped around five Key Exploitable Results (KERs) from which the community could derive benefits and make use of, and each of them refers to one or more of the identified target groups of iMagine (see figure below):

1. A portfolio of proven, operational AI services available to the relevant domain researchers and the wider EOOSC and AI4EU user communities (KER1).
2. A portfolio of new AI services that have been technologically validated in the relevant environments, which would be further developed after the project (KER2).
3. A large collection of high-quality image repositories (KER3).
4. iMagine framework for developing, testing, training, deploying, and running AI-based models and imaging applications (KER4).
5. Lessons learnt and best practice documentation for adoption and deployment of AI in image analysis services (KER5).

The project has five expected impact points, as detailed in the following:

Outcome 1: Improved acquisition, quality, interoperability and analysis of imaging data from different disciplines.

Outcome 2: Wider use of image analysis services based on AI in different scientific areas.

Impact 1: Reinforced RI capacity to provide at scale and across the EU to support excellent research to address societal challenges and Horizon Europe missions and partnerships' objectives.

Impact 2: Enhanced and increased society's long-term and consistent problem-solving capacity and evidence-based policy making, including a better understanding of socio-economic implications, through providing innovative, customised and efficient RI services.

Impact 3: New discoveries and knowledge breakthroughs enabled by access provision to the best and, in some cases, unique state-of-the-art RIs.

Impact 4: A new generation of researchers trained to optimally exploit all the essential and advanced tools for their research.

Impact 5: Cross-fertilization and a wider sharing of knowledge and technologies across disciplines and between academia and industry, and businesses.

Both the outcomes and the impacts will be communicated appropriately to emphasise the contribution of iMagine to the specific results and achievements.

Figure 3. Relation among KERs and Target Groups

Communication toolbox

Channels

There are several communications channels available for dissemination and engagement in iImagine.

Website

The [website](#) is the main source of information about the project's progress and development; it is updated regularly and includes information on the status of the use cases, the iImagine AI platform, the best practices produced by the partners, and any other useful information that might arise. Hosted at EGI, it uses Matomo for analytics and insights on user visits to the website.

Social Media

In addition to the website, iMagine has **social media channels** on [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#) that will progressively become more active to disseminate the achieved results and milestones.

Note that, rather than focusing on absolute numbers for reporting social media activities, the project will base its social media 'success' on two parameters: regularity (as in: all relevant content advertised) and audience engagement rate (benchmarked against other, similar, accounts). To this extent, the project will use the Hootsuite platform of EGI to monitor engagement and uptake best.

Also, given the current uncertainty related to Twitter, the project is on the look-out for viable alternatives (such as Mastodon). No decision has been taken.

Depending on the target audience, content and message will be adapted and published on the appropriate channel.

Scientific Conferences and Policy Events

Events represent an excellent opportunity for the dissemination and promotion of the results of iMagine.

Project events

In particular, the project will organise three workshops framed under the umbrella of the Competence Centre to be established with IT, AI and domain experts on the advanced use of e-infrastructures and AI for scientific image analysis. Whenever possible, project meetings and events will be co-located with the EGI conferences in 2023, 2024 and 2025.

Other events

Moreover, iMagine partners have already started seeking opportunities for dissemination with the participation of project representatives in external events that are both discipline-specific (marine science) or technology-related (AI events), in addition to cross-disciplinary opportunities. These events include: the IODE Ocean Data Conference, the European Geoscience Union annual conference, the Marine Imaging Workshop and others. Partners are encouraged to involve iMagine in any events they organise, suggesting potential dissemination venues for coordination and notifying the communications team of any successful proposals.

The partners should use the resources available in the Communication Toolkit (see below) to prepare their presentations and presence at events; WP2 is available to produce ad-hoc dissemination materials on request. Partners are invited to share their material when useful for the entire project.

Scientific publications

Scientific publications are the most outstanding ways to communicate findings in the community and among peers. They need to acknowledge the funding received from iMagine in the acknowledgements section and the publication metadata. T2.2 is available for minimal proofreading, advice and optimisation of visuals; however, it will not take any

responsibility regarding the publication's content, nor will T2.2 prompt partners to write scientific publications, as this is part of their research activities.

Partners commit themselves to deposit a post-print version of their article in a repository, e.g. institutional or the iImagine Zenodo community mentioned below, and to make the final version available as open access in accordance with the Commission's Open Science Policies.

WP2 will ensure wide promotion of the open-access versions of these publications by amplifying on social media and listing them on the project website.

Newsletter

For periodic communications, iImagine will rely on the **EGI newsletter**, which has over 2,500 recipients and a wide reach, especially among those interested in technology, Research Infrastructures and EOSC developments. However, there is no user segmentation specifically dedicated to iImagine, at the moment; to solve this, targeted communications campaigns will be used to attract specific audiences to subscribe to the newsletter, therefore enabling more refined communication towards the stakeholders. Moreover, collaboration will be sought with the identified similar initiatives to maximise the dissemination of the iImagine results and impact.

Repositories

Zenodo

iImagine maintains a [community on Zenodo](#); in addition to serving the purpose of keeping the live archive of the project documentation (deliverables, publications and any other written document), that community also multiplies the visibility of those outputs, which is, in the end, beneficial for the project purposes.

Confluence

[Confluence](#) is the main source for internal project documentation. Access is limited to consortium members.

Similar initiatives and the EOSC

The project will map similar initiatives (such as AI4Life, funded in the same call, but also any other relevant EU-wide initiatives) about marine science and AI to inform them about the iImagine developments and possibly collaborate to disseminate further. Moreover, the iImagine AI platform will be based on the EOSC Compute Platform and be available through the EOSC Marketplace to provide access and outreach to many researchers in the aquatic domain, leveraging on the collaboration with the major Research Infrastructures in the field of marine science.

Mailing lists

A set of mailing lists is available to ease communication in the project; in addition to the general one, there are dedicated mailing lists to each work package and to the iImagine project management team. EGI manages these mailing lists as the project coordinator.

Materials

A [communications toolkit](#) is available for the iImagine partners to use; it includes several assets ready to use and will be enriched during the project development to reflect the evolution of the technology. In the package, partners can find:

- The project logo in different variations
- The project colours and instructions on how to use them
- A moo card with a QR code pointing to the website
- A roll-up banner design with the project objectives
- A project poster with a high-level description of the project – to be updated periodically to reflect the status of the project progress
- Zoom backgrounds
- Social media banners
- Document templates: a presentation template and a deliverable template are available
- A general presentation of the project and the eight use cases

Selected resources of the communications toolkit will also be available on the iImagine website for broader visibility and reuse, in the form of a media kit, alongside with the project brand guide.

Next steps

Among the support resources that will be developed in the first year of the project, there are:

- a presentation of the use cases in the form of a printable brochure
- a general flyer about the project
- an infographic showing the connection between the use cases and the research infrastructures relevant to them

In addition to that, the website will continuously be enriched with the following content, to be reused on social media for wider visibility:

- A news item describing the iImagine AI platform architecture, to be possibly featured on the EOSC Portal
- News items for each public deliverable that could be interesting for the wider public accepted until the next plan update:
 - D2.2 Innovation Management and Exploitation Plan
 - D2.3 FAIR assessment, EOSC and AI4EU liaison and integration plan

D2.1 First Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan

- D3.1 Technical development roadmap for the mature AI image analysis use cases
- D4.1 Best practices and guideline for developers and providers of AI-based image analytics services
- D4.2 Periodical assessment of AI and Infrastructure services
- D5.1 Periodical assessment of Imaging VA services
- News items for each of the use cases, starting with the mature ones and then moving to the prototypes
- News items for each event in which iMagine has been presented with a link to the respective presentation on Zenodo
- News items for any documentations or publications available from the project

Each of the above will be communicated to the respective partners for support in the dissemination of the news on their ends.

WP2 will support the organisation of the project events and, when possible, co-locate project activities with the EGI Conferences.

Provide logistical support for the organisation of the technical workshops.

Measure progress and impact

The communications measure iMagine will adopt to monitor the activities and the desired impact of the project are described below. In the course of the projects, these will be further refined and adjusted based on the results provided by the implementation of those outlined here.

Target Groups	Identified ways of engagement	Activity	Objective	Key messages	Channel	Measure	Timing
Users	Concrete example: The project will inform the target group about the portfolio of services through a variety of dissemination activities, which will in turn be further communicated to researchers and	Create and maintain (online) engagement channels	Keep users informed about the project activities and invite them to interact	"The objective of our project is..." "We are currently working on..." "We invite you to download..."	Website, social media, newsletters, events	# Page visits # engagement rate on social media (3%), # clicks on project-related content in EGI newsletter, # attendees during presentations at events leading to an indication (e.g., feedback, low # requests for more information) that the audience understands the	M1-36

D2.1 First Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan

Target Groups	Identified ways of engagement	Activity	Objective	Key messages	Channel	Measure	Timing
	other users. These end users will be able to improve the efficiency of their research activities, due to the clear demonstration of the results (e.g., the service portfolio) and its accessibility.					project.	
		Promote use cases	Show users the solutions to challenges they are tackling	"Use case X uses service X and tackles environmental challenges through the impact of X, Y, Z."	Website, email, brochures	# Use cases clicked on the website, # times use cases brochures downloaded, leading to an indication (e.g., feedback, presentations) that the audience understands and exploits the use cases.	M5-M36
		Inform users how to access and use the outputs of the project (services, IT platform, Image repository etc.)	Facilitate the ease of accessing and using services and platforms for users, communities, research infrastructures	"Visit this page to get access to the service portfolio." "Join our webinar on service X." "Participate in the training"	Website, dedicated social media campaigns, events, webinars, training	# Page visits #engagement rate on social media, # attendees during presentations at events, # attendees at webinars and training, leading to an indication (e.g.,	M5-M36

D2.1 First Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan

Target Groups	Identified ways of engagement	Activity	Objective	Key messages	Channel	Measure	Timing
				series of service X."		new use cases) that the audience uses the outputs of the project correctly.	
Infrastructure providers	Concrete example: The project informs the target group about the infrastructure needs through a variety of dissemination activities	Share news on the progress of the iMagine AI platform	Create awareness about the project, its activities and the infrastructural needs	"The services running on the iMagine AI platform require X and Y compute capacity/storage"	Newsletter, events, email	# Clicks on newsletter item, interaction during events/email, leading to an indication (e.g., request for collaboration / more information) that the audience understands how to contribute to the iMagine infrastructure/what are the infrastructure needs	M7-M36
Similar AI initiatives	Concrete example: The project	Share news items on project objectives and	Create awareness about the project and its	"The project aims to support (environmenta	Newsletter, events, EOOSC platforms, email	# Clicks on newsletter item, interaction during events/email,	M5-M36

D2.1 First Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan

Target Groups	Identified ways of engagement	Activity	Objective	Key messages	Channel	Measure	Timing
	complements the dissemination activities of the AI4EU project, with the available service portfolio and dedicated IT platform, which supports showcasing the relevance and importance of AI initiatives in Europe.	activities	activities (additionally to show potential coordinated communication and dissemination strategies)	l) research through easy access to AI services." "The project uses AI services to..."		leading to an indication (e.g., request for collaboration / more information) that the audience understands the benefits of the project for the (shared) AI environment.	
Decision and policy makers	Concrete example: The impact of the offered services, mainly presented through use cases, will directly show which local challenges can be	Inform about the project and its importance for the environment and society	Showcase importance of project to national / regional policies and investments and to EU-level policymakers	"The project outputs contribute to tackling problems X, Y and Z." "The project is important because of..."	Website, newsletter, events, email	# Page visits, # clicks on relevant items in newsletter, leading to an indication (e.g., request for impact reports) that the audience will exploit the project outcome to influence policies	M10-M36

D2.1 First Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan

Target Groups	Identified ways of engagement	Activity	Objective	Key messages	Channel	Measure	Timing
	<p>addressed due to the project results. This will allow policymakers to get a better understanding of the impact such solutions can have.</p> <p>Concrete example: The impact of the offered services, mainly presented through use cases, will directly show which contributions they can provide to policymaking activities in the environmental</p>					# materials download	

D2.1 First Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan

Target Groups	Identified ways of engagement	Activity	Objective	Key messages	Channel	Measure	Timing
	and marine science areas.						
Service and content providers	Concrete example: The project gives visibility to the providers, and their services and content are available in the dedicated portfolio and IT platform	Communicate about possibilities to offer / highlight services	Ensure the target audience is aware of the opportunities to offer their services and promote / highlight these through the project	"The project aims to create service portfolios that will be widely disseminated, add your service."	Website, Direct email, Newsletter, Specific call for services	# Page visits # clicks on item in newsletter, # responses to call/informal inquiries to onboard service, leading to an indication (e.g., request to offer service) that the audience understands the opportunities.	M10-M36
General public	Concrete example: Whoever is interested in environment and marine science can get information about the project's	Increase visibility of the project, by creating a brand identity and media pack	Ensure this audience recognises the project and is aware of the material to use when referring to the project	"Download our Style guide / media pack." "The project's name is ..." "Discover our use cases"	Website	# Downloads on communication material/media pack, # page visits on the 'about' page, leading to an indication that the audience knows what the project	M6-M36

D2.1 First Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan

Target Groups	Identified ways of engagement	Activity	Objective	Key messages	Channel	Measure	Timing
	objectives and be informed on the status of the use cases					looks like and where to find the branding/communication material # download of the use cases brochure	
Private sector	Concrete example: Companies that are working on specific monitoring activities will benefit from the results of the project in order to make their activities more efficient.	Communicate about possibilities to benefit from the use case discoveries and the services offered through the iMagine AI platform	Ensure the audience is aware of the project status and developments and how to get in touch if interested	“Discover our use cases developing X and Y with this and that possible uses for private sector”	Website, email, newsletter	# Page visits # clicks on item in newsletter # responses to emails	M10–M36
Organisations / agencies from different disciplines	Concrete example: NGOs will become aware of the project	Inform these organisations about the status of the uses cases	Ensure the audience is aware of the project status and	“Discover our use cases tackling this and that aspect of	Website, email, newsletter	# Downloads on communication material/media pack, # page visits	M10–M36

Target Groups	Identified ways of engagement	Activity	Objective	Key messages	Channel	Measure	Timing
	results and present the use cases and impact of the services to strengthen their lobby activities. Specialised training centres will in turn also be able to use the impact of the project results, merely to improve their training programmes.	and their achievements and developments, inform them of any events where to find iMagine	developments and what materials they can use to support their lobby activities	(insert topic)" "Visit us at this event to learn more about our use cases" "Download the brochure of our use cases"		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - About - Use cases # download of the use cases brochure	

Table 3. Foreseen activities to measure progress and impact

The table below recaps the engagement activities that will be developed in the project period covered by this deliverable.

Target group	Objective	Type of engagement activity	Timeline
Users	To inform the target group about the portfolio of services, with the suggestion to act as a multiplier to researchers and other users.	Promote use cases	M5-M20
		Inform users how to access and use the outputs of the project (services, IT platform, Image repository etc.)	M5-M20
Infrastructure providers	To inform the target group about the infrastructure needs.	Identify the infrastructures and share news on the progress of the iMagine AI platform	M7-M20
Similar AI initiatives	Complement the dissemination activities of the AI4EU project and showcase the relevance and importance of AI initiatives in Europe.	Establish cross-communications channels with them; share news items on the project objectives and activities.	M5-M20
Decision and policy makers	Demonstrate which local challenges can be addressed with the project results, to allow stakeholders to get a better understanding of the impact such solutions can have.	Inform about the project and its importance for the environment and society	M10-M36

Target group	Objective	Type of engagement activity	Timeline
Service and content providers	Give visibility to the providers, their services and content available in the dedicated portfolio, and IT platform	Communicate about opportunities and promote the services	M10-M20
General public	Provide information about the project's objectives and be informed on the status of the use cases	Increase visibility of the project, by creating a brand identity and media pack and point to it when needed.	M6-M20
Private sector	Companies that are working on specific monitoring activities will benefit from the results of the project to make their activities more efficient.	Identify relevant companies in the field; communicate about possibilities to benefit from the use case discoveries and the services offered through the iMagine AI platform	M10-M20
Organisations, agencies from different disciplines	Make NGOs aware of the project results and present the use cases and impact of the services to strengthen their lobby activities.	Inform these organisations about the status of the uses cases and their achievements and developments, and inform them of any events where to find iMagine	M10-M20

Table 4. Recap of the engagement activities planned

Acronyms

AI Artificial Intelligence

RI Research Infrastructures

AI4EU (project) AI on-demand platform to support research excellence in Europe

EOSC European Open Science Cloud

KER Key Exploitable Result

NGO Non-governmental organisation

UC Use Case